

USE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF
TEACHING SCIENCES IN THE ENERGY FIELD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7857712>

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the optimization and effectiveness of the professional training of future employees in the field of electric power. The article substantiates the possibilities of innovative pedagogical technologies in solving these problems, as well as the role of the energy sector in the formation of readiness to implement innovative pedagogical activities in the future.*

Keywords: *pedagogical education, modernization, innovative innovative approach, pedagogical innovations, innovative pedagogical technologies.*

In our era of rapidly developing scientific and technical development, a new direction vector is being taken as a basis in vocational education, and more and more advanced and innovative methods and techniques are being introduced into the educational process of educational institutions.

In modern socio-economic conditions, the level of education, the effectiveness of the educational institution for training highly qualified competitive specialists depends to a large extent on the effectiveness of the introduction of educational technologies based on new methodological principles, modern didactic principles and psychological-pedagogical principles. depends.

Pedagogical theories that develop an active approach to education.

The main feature of any educational technology is its focus on clearly defined goals, defining the principles and development of methods for optimizing the learning process, as well as the assessment methods used. Therefore, the general characteristics of modern teaching technologies in educational institutions can be formulated as follows:

- focusing on new methodological principles and modern didactic principles that reveal the mechanisms of knowledge acquisition;

- comprehensive development of the student's personality, ensuring the efficiency of information reproduction, as well as developing creative thinking by increasing the content and structure of information, qualitatively changing the motivational component of education;

Achievements in a number of results in the process of educational and cognitive activity:

- the ability to determine the directions and methods of self-awareness in the surrounding socio-cultural environment in the conditions of technogenicity and the rapid increase of information content;

- the need for continuous effective stimulation of intellectual development, the need for active, purposeful self-education, the formation of appropriate psychological qualities of a person necessary in the information society;

- to ensure proper initial training and to create conditions for obtaining broad basic education, formation of professional skills and qualifications;

- the growth of the professional direction of education in educational institutions ensures the optimization and harmonization of the process of turning a student into a bright

personality of a specialist. All this improves the continuous process of formation of professional skills and abilities.

Modern technologies should be understood not only as information technologies aimed at intensive use of a personal computer, but also as technologies that are important for developing students' creative abilities, improving the methodology of organizing independent work, and developing logic.

New modern technologies of teaching is a set of forms, methods, tools, techniques that allow students to receive quality education. It is common to refer to them: modular rating, integrated teaching, information technologies of education. Regardless of the chosen educational technology, it is necessary to pursue the main goal of achieving high results in the formation of students' knowledge, in solving the issue of activating the educational process, that is, in the first place, in the use of new and effective methods and methods.

The problem of solving pedagogical innovations in the educational process first of all, it should be understood the purposeful activity of the teacher related to the development and application of such forms, methods and educational tools that help to increase the interest and activity of students.

To achieve the goal of improving the knowledge and skills of students in the study of specialized subjects, it is necessary to use the latest methods and methods of teaching.

Integrated education- teaching technology based on the complex solution of each problem. Today, an integrated approach to learning is not only relevant, but promising. The construction of integrated type of science education meets the tasks of person-oriented education, as it allows determining the student's attitude to the surrounding world.

An integrated approach- this is to create a holistic picture of reality, a "picture of the world".

The principles of integrated education include:

- presentation of educational material on a comprehensive basis;
- formation of holistic knowledge;
- development of personal potential.

The purpose of integrated education is to create optimal conditions for the student's development and self-awareness through the formation of comprehensive knowledge about the studied object.

The goals of integrated education in the study of specialized subjects are:

- reveal the student's personal potential;
- formation of skills of interest, real motives;
- to stimulate the mechanism of self-expression and self-awareness of the student.

Integration includes the search for joint platforms for the convergence of scientific knowledge and the acquisition of new ones at the intersection of traditional knowledge; to combine the efforts of teachers of different subjects, to combine knowledge about a certain object of study obtained through different educational subjects.

In education interactivity can be explained as the ability to learn in the mode of interaction, conversation, dialogue, action. Therefore, literally, such a method can be called interactive, in which the participant who is reading, that is, does something:

- speaks;

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- manages;
- models;
- writes

He does not act as a listener or observer, but actively participates in the happenings.

Interactive education in the study of specialized subjects is a special form of organizing cognitive activity, which has a specific goal - to create comfortable learning conditions in which each student feels his success, intellectual ability.

The essence of interactive education is that the learning process is carried out in the conditions of constant, active interaction of all students. This is joint education and mutual education (community, group, cooperative learning), in which both the teacher and the student are equal, equivalent subjects of education. The organization of interactive education involves simulating life situations, using role-playing games, and solving problems together based on the analysis of situations. It effectively helps in the formation of skills and abilities, and in the formation of values.

Interactive forms and methods of teaching in the study of specialized subjects, unlike traditional ones, are more effective in mastering the educational material, encourage students to work creatively and form their personal position in understanding the educational content.

The main advantages of interactive forms and methods are the creation of a cooperative environment according to the scheme: teacher - student, student - student, student - computer.

The main goal of this educational technology is the way to develop a person and form a personal worldview. The basis of student motivation is achievement and self-realization of the individual.

Information technology of education such a model of the educational process is understood, in which the goal is achieved through the full use of computer and software capabilities.

The purpose of this educational technology is to prepare students for a favorable state of health in the information society.

In the study of sciences in the field of energy, new information technologies offer the following:

- Activation of training;
- Formation of students' information culture.

Therefore, the methods of activating learning are such methods of pedagogical actions that encourage students to active thinking, creative, research approaches in the search for truth in science and practice.

Pedagogical technologies used in the study of sciences in the field of energy allow to involve every student in active cognitive activity and this helps to develop critical thinking, dialogic speech, ability to prove, students acquire the skills of cooperation, team research. actively participate in solutions, learning and transferring their knowledge to others.

In the process of preparing for practical work, he acquires a creative approach to theory and applies the acquired knowledge in practice, gradually develops the skills of independent work on theoretical material, analyzes and develops the ability to draw conclusions.

REFERENCES

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL CONFERENCE
“DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF PRACTICAL
IMPLEMENTATION IN THE SPHERES”**

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1. The introduction of innovative technologies into the educational process is one of the factors of raising the competitiveness of future specialists to a new level// Organization of the educational process. Work experience of higher education institutions of I-II accreditation level. Issue 9, pp. 180-195.
2. Introduction of interactive technologies // Organization of educational process. Work experience of higher education institutions of I-II accreditation level. Issue 9, pp. 161-174
3. Morse NV Distance technology as the basis of modern information technologies in education// New technologies of education. Scientific-methodical collection. Issue 30, pp. 32-42